

Effect of blue green algae (BGA) on rice yield at different locations and residual effect on gram

G. Ram, Agricultural Research Station (ARS), Sarkanda, Bilaspur, and A. K. Rawat, Jawaharlal Nehru Krishi Vidyalaya (JNKVV), Jabalpur Pin 482004 Madhya Pradesh (MP), India

We studied the effect of BGA on rice yields in multilocal trials by the JNKVV ARS in Bilaspur, MP, from 1979 to 1983 (Table 1). Applying 10 kg BGA inoculum/ha increased grain yield (14%).

Table 1. Grain yield with and without BGA, JNKVV.

Location	Grain yield (t/ha)		Increase in grain yield	
	Control (no BGA)	With 10 kg BGA/ha	t/ha	%
1979				
Sarkanda	3.4	4.1	0.7	19
Khoksa	3.2	3.5	0.3	10
Gorela	2.6	3.0	0.3	13
Ragja	1.1	1.1	0.1	7
1980				
Barkanda	3.4	4.0	0.6	18
Khoksa	3.0	3.4	0.4	13
Pendra	2.6	3.0	0.4	15
Dharampura	1.5	2.0	0.5	33
1981				
Sarkanda	2.4	2.8	0.4	17
Khoksa	1.7	2.0	0.3	19
Ragja	3.0	3.4	0.3	11
Lormi	2.6	3.0	0.4	15
Korba	2.7	3.0	0.3	13
Katghora	1.4	1.6	0.2	16
Gorela	2.8	3.1	0.3	10
1982				
Sarkanda	4.0	4.6	0.7	17
Jali	1.3	1.4	0.2	12
Kudri	2.2	2.3	0.2	7
Janjgir	2.4	2.5	0.2	6
Khisora	3.4	3.8	0.4	12
Khatola	2.4	2.8	0.4	17
Sakti	2.6	2.8	0.2	8
Churi	3.5	4.0	0.5	14
Pali	3.4	3.8	0.3	9
1983				
Bilaspur	2.3	2.8	0.5	20
Bilaspur	2.9	3.4	0.6	20
Mungeli	1.8	2.0	0.2	9
Mungeli	1.6	1.8	0.2	14
Lormi	3.4	3.6	0.2	5
Lormi	2.9	3.0	0.2	6
Pamgarh	2.8	3.2	0.4	14
Pamgarh	1.7	2.1	0.4	22
Katghora	3.5	4.5	1.0	29
Katghora	5.5	6.3	0.9	16
Av	2.7	3.1	0.4	14

Table 2. Grain yield with NPK and BGA at 4 locations, JNKVV.

Treatment (kg/ha)	Grain yield (t/ha)							
	1979				1981			
	Sarkanda	Khoksa	Ragja	Pendra	Ragja	Khoksa	Sarkanda	Sarkanda
Control	3.4	3.2	1.0	2.6	3.0	1.7	23.58	4.0
10 BGA,	4.1	3.5	1.1	3.0	3.4	2.0	27.58	4.6
20-40-15 NPK	-	-	-	-	3.3	2.7	30.47	5.3
20-40-15 NPK + 10 BGA	-	-	-	-	3.7	2.8	30.43	6.0
40-40-15 NPK	4.3	3.2	1.2	3.3	3.8	2.6	32.57	5.5
40-40-15 NPK + 10 BGA	4.4	3.4	1.5	3.8	3.8	2.8	35.77	6.2
60-60-15 NPK	5.3	4.1	1.6	4.0	4.0	2.6	39.06	6.2
60-60-15 NPK + 10 BGA	-	-	-	-	4.0	2.9	39.29	6.5
CD at 5%	-	0.6	-	-	0.4	0.6	0.4	1.2

Trials in 1979, 1981, and 1982 (Table 2) show that applying 10 kg BGA/ha saves 20-40 kg N/ha.

In 1979, we evaluated the yield of Bengal gram planted after rice to determine the residual effect of 10 kg BGA inoculation/ha to rice (Table 3); BGA was inoculated before rice transplanting. Gram was drilled immediately after rice harvest without plowing the field. No fertilizer was applied and the crop was grown without management. Table 3

Table 3. Yield of rice and gram after rice, JNKVV.

Treatment (kg/ha)	Rice yield (t/ha)	Gram yield (t/ha)
Control	3.4	1.2
10 BGA	4.1	1.8
40-40-15 NPK	4.3	1.8
40-40-15 NPK + 10 BGA	4.4	1.4

shows that BGA increased rice and gram yield. □

Yield response of upland rice to NPK fertilization with burned rice husk

A. A. Jakhro, Institute of Agriculture, Timbang Menggaris 102, Kota Belud, Sabah, Malaysia

We conducted a field experiment to determine the effect of applying N, P, and K with and without burned rice husk. Soil was a Gleyic Luvisol with 32.1% sand, 36.8% silt, 31.1% clay, pH 5.3, 1.36% organic carbon, 0.18% total N, 37 ppm available P, 0.5 meq exchangeable K/100

g, and 16.74 meq cation exchange capacity/100 g.

Before direct-seeding 120 kg IR42 seeds/ha, 10 t burned rice husk/ha was evenly applied and incorporated. Seeds

Table 2. Effect of NPK fertilizer and burned rice husk on grain yield of upland rice, Sabah, Malaysia.

Fertilizer applied (kg/ha) NPK	Grain yield ^a (t/ha)			
	Without rice husk		With rice husk	
0-0-0	0.9	i	1.5	i
50-0-0	1.3	gh	2.3	def ^g
100-0-0	1.6	ef	2.7	def ^g
150-0-0	1.9	e	2.9	cd
0-13-0	1.0	i	1.8	h
50-13-0	2.4	cd	3.0	c
100-13-0	2.6	c	3.9	a
150-13-0	2.9	b	3.8	a
0-13-25	1.4	fg	2.8	def
50-13-25	2.6	c	3.0	c
100-13-25	3.1	b	3.1	c
150-13-25	3.5	a	3.3	b

^aIn a column, means followed by a common letter are not significantly different at the 0.05 level by DMRT.

Table 1. Weekly rainfall distribution during crop season, Sabah, Malaysia.

Mo	Rainfall (mm)				
	Wk1	Wk2	Wk3	Wk4	Total
Jul	85.0	12.0	18.1	12.2	127.3
Aug	24.1	32.0	0	43.1	99.2
Sep	0	0	68.5	36.0	104.5
Oct	58.4	81.1	15.6	4.8	159.9
Nov	11.0	4.2	19.0	41.6	75.8